

An experimental review with preliminary “ex vivo” analysis of tumor thermal ablation mediated by magnetic nanoparticles using multiparametric MRI- A study at a tertiary hospital in South India

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ABSTRACT:

Purpose: This study evaluates the efficacy of tumor thermal ablation mediated by magnetic nanoparticles using multiparametric MRI in an experimental rat model of colorectal liver metastases, aiming to quantify thermal increases and assess tissue effects. **Materials and Methods:** Eighteen male WAG/RijCrl rats underwent tumor induction via subcapsular injection of syngeneic colon adenocarcinoma cells. Magnetic fluid, comprising 25nm Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles suspended in Clinoleic® 20%, was infused intratumorally under ultrasound guidance in ten rats with confirmed tumors. MRI studies assessed infusion accuracy. Ex vivo livers were subjected to radiofrequency (RF) fields (12.5–16KA/m, 250–699KHz) for thermal induction, with temperature monitored in tumor tissue and immersion media (saline or distilled water). Histological analysis used hematoxylin-eosin and Perls blue staining to evaluate thermal lesions and iron deposits. **Results:** Tumors (33–480 mm³) were successfully infused with 3.5–5.5 mg of nanoparticles. Thermal induction in saline-immersed livers showed significant temperature increases proportional to RF frequency and nanoparticle dose, while distilled water immersion limited heating to tumor tissue. No thermal lesions were observed histologically, but iron deposits and necrotic pathways from injections were noted. **Conclusion:** Ultrasound-guided nanoparticle infusion effectively localized magnetic particles within tumors. RF-induced thermal increases were observed, influenced by immersion media and nanoparticle concentration. Further studies are needed to optimize thermal ablation for tissue necrosis and evaluate adjacent tissue effects.

Keywords: magnetic nanoparticles, thermal ablation, colorectal liver metastases, multiparametric MRI, radiofrequency.

INTRODUCTION:

Colorectal cancer, one of the most frequent neoplastic processes in the Western world, generates a high volume of metastatic liver disease¹. Currently, the best therapeutic option for liver metastases is surgical excision, however, this treatment is only applicable in 8-27% of those affected. For those patients who are not candidates for surgery², local therapeutic options have been developed such as percutaneous transmural ablation techniques or transarterial procedures for tumor

embolization, chemoembolization or radioembolization³. However, the uneven overall success of these non-surgical therapies makes it necessary to investigate new alternatives.

Magnetic nanoparticles are substances capable of generating a hyperthermia-inducing energy transfer when exposed to a radiofrequency (RF) emitting system⁴. Their clinical use has been tested in different types of tumors, especially in prostate cancer. In the liver, an experimental therapeutic option consists of the

direct intratumoral injection of a suspension of magnetic nanoparticles⁵, so that they are deposited in the neoplastic tissue. In this location, and after exposure to an external magnetic field, the suspension or magnetofluid would cause thermal ablation of the tumor tissue⁶.

In order to be used in thermotherapy for hepatic neoplastic pathology, we have developed a magnetic fluid based on a suspension of iron oxide nanoparticles in Clinoleic[®] 20% (BAXTER SA). Thus, in an experimental oncological model induced in rat liver, the present experiment aims to quantify the thermal increase achieved in tumors injected with the magnetic fluid and subsequently subjected to an external RF inducer⁷.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

Animals:

The experimental study was performed on 18 male WAG/RijCrl rats, 2.5 months old and weighing 211-263 g. All procedures were carried out in accordance with the current state legislation regarding the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes, after obtaining clearance from the ethical cum scientific advisory committee.

Magnetic Fluid:

The magnetofluid was prepared from 25nm Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles. During the synthesis process, the nanoparticles were surrounded by lipid organic ligands, which, by means of ultrasound, allowed their suspension in Clinoleic[®] 20%, a combination of purified olive oil (80%) and soybean oil (20%) whose use is indicated in parenteral nutrition. In this way, suspensions of between 3.5 and 5.5 mg of iron oxide nanoparticles in 0.4 ml of Clinoleic[®] 20% were prepared, which would later be individually infused into each animal, by percutaneous intratumoral route.

Anesthesia:

During the tumor inoculation process, animals were kept under Halothane-induced inhalation anesthesia.

For the practice of ultrasound examinations, intratumoral infusion of magnetic fluids, and MRI studies, intraperitoneal anesthesia was used based on an injection of Diazepam (25 mg/kg) combined ten minutes later with Ketamine (100 mg/kg).

Tumor induction:

On day 0 of the experiment, the animals underwent a subxiphoid median laparotomy to expose the liver. A direct subcapsular puncture was then performed in the left hepatic lobe to inject 25,000 syngeneic colon adenocarcinoma cells (cell line: CC-531) suspended in 0.05 ml of Hank's solution.

Control of tumor development:

To monitor the development and progression of hepatic neoplastic lesions, animals underwent serial abdominal ultrasounds at 21 and 28 days after tumor injection. Ultrasounds were performed on an Esaote "MyLab60 XVision" ultrasound system equipped with a 6-18 MHz multi-frequency linear probe (Fig. 1).

Rats that did not show tumor development were sacrificed. In animals that showed neoplastic masses, tumor volume was calculated using the formula: largest diameter x (smallest diameter)² / 2

Magnetofluid ultrasound-guided infusion procedure

On day 28, the magnetofluids were infused intratumorally in ten animals that had developed neoplastic lesions. The maximum diameters of the tumors were: median 8 mm (range: 10-4 mm). The infusion procedure was performed by direct transparietal puncture of the neoplastic lesions, guided by ultrasound and with a free-hand technique (See Scientific Electronic Presentation: "Preliminary "ex vivo" experiment of tumor thermoablation mediated by magnetic nanoparticles. Process I: image monitoring of intratumoral infusion"). After verifying the correct intratumoral location of the needle, the magnetofluids were slowly instilled inside the tumors (Fig. 2). In the case of large tumors, two or three punctures were required, in different places, to reach most of the neoplastic tissue. Once all the fluid had been administered, the needle was withdrawn and pressure was applied to the liver surface with the ultrasound probe itself to promote hemostasis.

MRI studies:

Six hours after the infusion of magnetofluids, MRI studies were performed to assess the suitability of the infusion.

Fig. 1 : Ultrasound monitoring of tumor development. A. Hyperechoic nodule measuring 27 mm in the left hepatic lobe, ultrasound scan 21 days after inoculation of neoplastic cells. B. After 28 days, the tumor lesion bulges on the hepatic surface and has a maximum diameter of 45 mm.

Induction procedure and thermal control:

On day 29, 18 hours after the infusion of magnetofluids, the animals were sacrificed by deep anesthesia and cervical dislocation. Subsequently, the livers of the six infused animals that had developed the largest tumor lesions, and of another non-infused rat that we would use as a control, were extracted.

Once the livers were removed, they were immersed in saline solution (n=5) or distilled water (n=2). Probes for temperature recording had been previously implanted inside the tumor lesions. A probe for thermal monitoring was also placed in the medium in which the livers were immersed.

The livers were then placed inside the RF induction coil (Fig. 3). After reaching thermal equilibrium between the probes placed inside the liver tissue and the perihepatic immersion medium, 20°C, the specimens were subjected,

for a maximum period of 30 minutes, to magnetic field strengths between 12.5 and 16KA/m, and frequencies up to 699KHz.

Histological analysis:

After completion of the thermal induction procedure, the livers were fixed in formalin for histopathological analysis. Representative sections of liver tissue and tumor tissue were obtained; the samples were stained with hematoxylin-eosin and Perls blue for subsequent study with optical microscopy. The first staining would be used to evaluate potential thermal tissue lesions, and the second staining would identify tissue deposits of injected iron.

Fig. 2 : Percutaneous magnetic fluid injection procedure. A. Arrows indicate the intratumoral location of the 30G needle used for injection. B. After administration of magnetofluid, the tumor (arrows) shows increased echogenicity.

RESULTS:

At 28 days after tumor injection, tumor involvement was detected in ten animals. The volume of the neoplasms ranged from 33 to 480 mm³, median 180 mm³.

The ten rats that had developed tumors were successfully infused with the suspensions and showed no adverse reactions to them. These animals were injected with 0.4 ml of magnetofluid containing between 3.5 and 5.5 mg of magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles.

In the six rats with larger lesions, the liver was removed to undergo thermal induction procedures and quantification of the possible thermal increase. The liver of one rat that had not been infused was also subjected to thermal induction. Two animals were subjected to a magnetic field frequency of 250 KHz and five others to a magnetic field frequency of 699 KHz.

Livers immersed in physiological saline solution experienced significant thermal increases both in the

immersion medium and in the tumor tissue, proportional to the frequencies of the magnetic field used and the amounts of magnetic nanoparticles injected. On the other hand, the liver infused and immersed in distilled water experienced a much smaller thermal increase, exclusive of the tumor tissue, while in the control liver no increase in temperature was observed.

Histological analysis of the samples did not show any lesions attributable to the increase in temperature. Linear intratumoral necrotic pathways caused by the injection of magnetofluids were observed. Abundant iron deposits were also identified around the necrotic pathways of the puncture, and also in Kupffer cells, macrophages and tumor glands (Fig.3)

Image 3: Hematoxylin-Eosin stain. An ocher deposit corresponds to the magnetofluid that has diffused between the tumor glandular formations.

CONCLUSION:

The ultrasound-guided percutaneous intratumoral infusion was a technically simple procedure that allowed a high concentration of magnetic nanoparticles to be selectively localized within tumor beds.

In the thermal induction process, when the physiological saline solution was used as an immersion medium for the livers, it was observed that the application of RF itself caused heating of the medium, probably due to the presence of salts dissolved in the serum itself. This thermal increase, in addition, was directly proportional to the frequency of the applied magnetic field.

In livers subjected to a higher field frequency, differences in thermal induction were also observed, which seemed proportional to the amount of iron administered. This observation suggests that the thermal increase obtained, in addition to having been caused by the physiological serum itself, was also to a certain extent caused by the injected magnetic nanoparticles.

Finally, in livers immersed in distilled water, the intratumoral thermal increase was only observed in the liver infused with nanoparticles.

In conclusion, it seems that the application of RF itself can cause, at high frequencies, thermal increases in biological media. On the other hand, our experiment has also shown that it is possible to induce a selective intratumoral thermal increase. Based on all this, new experiments should be carried out to obtain higher thermal increases, capable of causing tissue necrosis, and possible undesirable effects on neighbouring tissues should also be evaluated and controlled.

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